

Abstract

Traditional Chinese Medicine for Infertility: Results of Research from the Last Years.

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Infertility is a significant global health issue affecting millions of individuals, necessitating the exploration of effective complementary treatments alongside conventional care. Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), specifically acupuncture and phytopharmacology, has gained increasing attention for its potential to improve reproductive outcomes. This communication presents a synthesis of recent high-level scientific evidence regarding the efficacy of TCM in treating both female and male infertility.

For female infertility, recent systematic reviews of high-quality randomized controlled trials (RCTs) highlight the following:

- **Chinese Phytopharmacology:** Interventions using formulas such as *Zishen Yutai*, *Dingkun*, and *Erzhi Tiangui* have shown significant increases in pregnancy rates, improved embryo quality, and enhanced endometrial receptivity.
- **Acupuncture:** Evidence suggests that acupuncture, used alone or as an adjunct therapy, provides promising results for conditions such as anovulatory infertility, polycystic ovary

syndrome (PCOS), and endometriosis. Clinical benefits include improved ovulation rates, increased endometrial thickness, and the modulation of reproductive hormones to facilitate embryo implantation.

Regarding male infertility, the research indicates that acupuncture can significantly enhance reproductive health by:

- Improving sperm quality, specifically increasing sperm motility and concentration.
- Restoring hormonal balance and reducing testicular damage caused by abnormal endocrine functions.
- Mitigating apoptosis in germ cells, thereby improving overall semen quality.

In conclusion, the research results from recent years validate TCM as a valuable adjunct therapeutic option in reproductive health. While some methodological limitations persist in the literature, the evidence increasingly supports the integration of these traditional practices to enhance fertility outcomes for both women and men.

Keywords: Infertility; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Acupuncture; Phytopharmacology; Reproductive Health.

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